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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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INDIVIDUAL DIAGNOSIS OF GENRE AND SPELLING ERRORS IN MOTHER TONGUE LESSONS THROUGH AI PROGRAMS

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Abstract: This article presents ideas on the individual diagnosis of spelling and grammar errors in native language classes through AI programs and discusses the current penetration of artificial intelligence technologies into all areas. The “Hybrid Diagnostics and Adaptive Feedback” method was used to correct spelling errors in students and improve their spelling literacy.

Key words: native language, spelling, grammar, spelling errors, artificial intelligence, students, education, writing.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ona tili darslarida husnixat va imlo xatolarini AI dasturlari orqali individual diagnostika qilish haqida fikrlar keltirilgan bo'lib, bugungi kunda barcha sohalarga sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining kirib kelishi haqida so'z yuritilgan. O'quvchilarda imlo xatolarini tuzatishda va imloviy savodxonligini oshirishda “Gibrid diagnostika va adaptiv qayta aloqa” metodidan foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ona tili, husnixat, imlo xatolari, sun'iy intellekt, o'quvchilar, ta'lim, yozuv.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены идеи индивидуальной диагностики орфографических и грамматических ошибок на уроках родного языка с помощью программ искусственного интеллекта, а также рассматривается современное внедрение технологий искусственного интеллекта во все сферы деятельности. Метод “Гибридная диагностика и адаптивная обратная связь” был использован для исправления орфографических ошибок у учащихся и повышения их орфографической грамотности.

Ключевые слова: родной язык, орфография, грамматика, орфографические ошибки, искусственный интеллект, учащиеся, образование, письмо.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of modern information and communication technologies and the expanding capabilities of artificial intelligence are bringing about fundamental changes in the field of education. In particular, the use of intelligent systems in the process of vocational education opens up wide opportunities for combining students' theoretical knowledge with practical skills and increasing their readiness for real work. At the heart of such approaches is the formation of an intellectual approach to understanding young people's professional activities, analyzing problems, finding solutions, and making decisions. Given the increasing demand for highly qualified, independent-thinking specialists who have mastered modern technologies in today's global labor market, the relevance of this topic is obvious ^[1].

Currently, the process of digitalization in education has begun to improve the quality of education. The penetration of digital technologies into all aspects of life requires a new quality of education from public employees. Changes are also taking place in the social sphere and in the field of education. Natural resources and cheap labor, although important, have become secondary factors of socio-economic development. The basic literacy that the current education system provides is no longer sufficient. A successful technological revolution always brings with it the means to solve the problems it creates, and digital information is no exception.

A person can convey thoughts to others in oral and written forms. There are similarities and differences between these two forms of speech, and each has its own advantages. Oral speech is spoken aloud and intended to be heard. It serves as a means of communication during interpersonal interaction. Written speech is recorded on stone, wood, leather, metal, or paper using permanent marks that are perceived visually. Writing is a powerful means of exchanging ideas and acquiring knowledge. Written speech connects generations and is preserved for long periods of time. Thanks to writing, people's thoughts and the knowledge acquired by humanity are passed down from generation to generation and preserved indefinitely.

The need to teach students to write beautifully in primary grades arises from these requirements. The methodology for teaching students to write beautifully in primary grades should enable them to write clearly, accurately, and quickly. To implement such tasks, it is necessary to analyze the content of the curriculum and its requirements, teaching methods, hygienic conditions for teaching writing, and individual shortcomings in students' handwriting, identify the causes of these shortcomings, and develop methods for correcting them.

Therefore, writing has significant pedagogical and social importance in a person's life. Teaching writing based on the above requirements begins in primary school. To teach students in grades 1–4 to write beautifully, the teacher must not only write beautifully but also be able to teach beautiful handwriting effectively. The science of calligraphy and its teaching is a practical discipline that performs not only the function of teaching beautiful handwriting but also educational and developmental functions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the important tasks facing our schools today is to improve students' literacy. Clean and beautiful handwriting plays a significant role in improving students' literacy. The great Russian pedagogue K. D. Ushinsky paid special attention to calligraphy lessons, stating that "initial orthographic skills are reinforced during calligraphy lessons" [8].

Uzbek schools began switching to writing based on Russian graphics in 1940. Although no special calligraphy manuals were created specifically for Uzbek schools, various methodological guides developed during that period were widely used. The manual *Teaching Calligraphy in Primary Schools*, compiled by V. A. Saglin in 1948, describes the goals and methods of teaching calligraphy in Grades I, II, III, and IV [7]. This book provides instructions for correcting typical handwriting errors and includes preparatory exercises for developing fluent writing skills.

The manual also contains rules for writing with chalk on the blackboard. In 1948, E. V. Guryanov compiled the manuals *Psychological Notes on Writing Exercises and Psychology and Methods of Teaching Writing in the Alphabetic Era*, in which the writing process is approached scientifically and the psychophysiological foundations of writing are explained [3,4,5]. In these manuals, the author draws attention to several conditions that increase the effectiveness of lessons in primary grades and provides practical recommendations.

In 1959, E. V. Guryanov's book *Psychology of Teaching Writing* was published [3]. This manual thoroughly explains the psychology of teaching writing and critiques the traditional calligraphic writing system. The author illustrates handwriting techniques with examples and recommends simplifying the existing graphic system of writing.

In the book *Teaching Writing*, written by D. A. Pisarevsky in 1983, methods for organizing handwriting lessons for primary school teachers were described for the first time.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The "Hybrid Diagnostics and Adaptive Feedback" method was used to individually diagnose handwriting and spelling errors in native language lessons for primary school students through AI programs.

Method Organization Process

1. Students Collect Information on the Topic

Spring has come. The days have become warmer. The trees have begun to sprout. Birds are flying in the streets. My mother waters the flowers in our yard. My father plants seedlings. My brother and I collect the leaves that have fallen to the ground. In spring, everything is clean and beautiful. When it rains, the air becomes even cleaner. I love spring because nature awakens and people's moods improve.

Students scan (or take a picture of) a dictation or independent assignment written in their native language notebook using a regular smartphone camera. Computer Vision and OCR (Optical Character Recognition) technologies (e.g., Google Lens or specialized AI programs) convert the handwriting into digital text.

2. Graphical Evaluation

The AI program compares the student's handwriting with a standard template. The slope of the letters, correct line alignment, spacing between letters, and letter connections are analyzed. The program identifies shortcomings in the handwriting (for example, the element of the letter "p" is written too low).

3. Linguistic Analysis

The digitized text is sent to NLP (Natural Language Processing) models (e.g., ChatGPT, Gemini API, or proofreading programs adapted to the Uzbek language corpus). The AI classifies the student's errors into the following categories:

1. Phonetic errors (omission or substitution of sounds);
2. Morphological errors (incorrect spelling of suffixes);
3. Punctuation errors (incorrect use or omission of punctuation marks).

Results

An automated report is generated for each student. Most importantly, the AI creates individualized corrective exercises based on the student's specific errors. For example, a student who frequently confuses the letters "X" and "H" is provided with an interactive game-based task involving only these letters.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1

Evaluation criteria	Traditional method	Hybrid AI diagnostic method
Check time	1 or 1.5 hours for 30 notebooks	A few minutes
Error statistics	In general, some errors may not be found.	Numerical and graphical statistics for each student
Task distribution	A common homework assignment for the class	individual assignments tailored to each student's mistakes

Today, the most effective way to fully integrate this approach into native language lessons is to use the following combination:

1. **Google Lens / Microsoft Lens:** To capture handwritten text and quickly convert it into digital text.
2. **LMS systems (e.g., Moodle, Google Classroom) with AI plugins:** To manage student databases and store diagnostic results.
3. **Prompt Engineering:** To analyze spelling and stylistic errors in texts by providing specially designed prompts to large language models such as GPT or Gemini in a way that is appropriate for the student's age and learning level.

Problems and Solutions

One challenge is that primary school students' handwriting skills are not yet fully developed. If a child writes letters unclearly or connects them excessively, artificial intelligence may fail to recognize the handwriting correctly or may misinterpret certain letters (for example, interpreting the letter combination "sh" as "w" or the letter "u" as "n").

Another challenge is that not every student has access to a tablet or smartphone, and the lack of high-speed Internet in classrooms can make it difficult to apply this method during lessons in real time.

To address these challenges, the method should be introduced gradually-not directly during classroom instruction, but through a blended learning approach, such as homework assessment or extracurricular club activities. Furthermore, selecting appropriate technical devices and integrating them effectively into the educational process largely depends on the pedagogical skills of the teacher.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Today, the status and development of every country are reflected in the educational potential of its younger generation. Therefore, teaching students correct writing skills from an early age, improving their literacy through calligraphy instruction, and helping them realize their full potential are among our primary responsibilities.

Modern pedagogy requires more than simply identifying students' mistakes and assigning low grades. Instead, it emphasizes identifying the root causes of those mistakes and guiding students toward overcoming them. Artificial intelligence can bring greater diagnostic accuracy and efficiency to native language lessons, enabling more personalized and effective learning experiences.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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